

METHODOLOGY OF CR ELEMENT RECOVERY DURING MELTING OF ALLOYED STEEL ALLOYS IN AN ELECTRIC ARC FURNACE

^{1,2} Kholmiraev N. B., ² Turdiev Sh. I., ¹ Akhmedova M. E., ¹ Pirvaliev D. A.,

¹ Gulmurodova G. G.

¹ Tashkent state technical university, Uzbekistan

² The association of building materials industry of Uzbekistan, R&D center, Uzbekistan

Article information:

Manuscript received: 21 Aug 2024; **Accepted:** 10 Sep 2024; **Published:** 10 Oct 2024

Abstract: This article presents a methodical analysis of the process of liquefaction of alloyed steel alloys in an electric arc furnace. That is, the processes of oxidation and reduction of chromium (Cr), one of the alloying elements, are considered. The conditions for the equilibrium of the temperature dependence of the amount of chromium and the completeness of oxidation of chromium dissolved in the metal during the liquefaction process are given.

Keywords: Chromium, metal-slag, oxidation, reduction, liquefaction, alloying elements, acid property, high-strength.

Introduction.

The industry's response to its unique local and global technologies is leading to gradual improvements in existing technologies as well as major changes in several important areas, such as steel and its alloys.

Steel is one of the most widely used metals in industrial production. As the global economy expands, the demand for steel and its alloys is growing rapidly, leading to increased supply needs [1-3].

High-strength alloy steels are used in the production of target components. These steels have better mechanical properties and corrosion resistance than conventional structural carbon steels. Because they are designed to respond not to chemical composition but to specific mechanical properties.

The main purposes of adding alloying elements to steel are:

- 1) improvement and expansion of existing properties of ordinary carbon steels;
- 2) development of new properties that do not exist in ordinary carbon steels.

Thus, the addition of a small amount of chromium leads to the improvement of its main properties, such as strength and purity, while a large amount of these elements also improves the properties of austenite, such as the stabilization of austenite at room temperature, the loss of magnetic properties, and very high resistance to corrosion [4-10].

Material and methods.

Today, the use of alloy steels is limited because they are expensive materials compared to plain

carbon steels.

The main influence of alloying elements on the microstructure and properties of steel can be classified as follows.

Influence of alloying elements on the formation and stability of carbides. Some alloying elements form very stable carbides when added to steel. This generally increases the hardness properties of steels, especially when the carbides formed are harder than iron carbide. One of these elements is chromium. It often forms intermediate compounds. Some of these elements form separate hard carbides in the microstructure, for example, Cr_7C_3 [11-14].

Chromium, like manganese, can be oxidized or reduced during smelting, depending on the composition of the metal and slag, as well as the temperature of the process. The oxidation (reduction) reaction of chromium occurs at the metal-slag interface and can lead to the formation of CrO and Cr_2O_3 . In acidic slag, chromium is found predominantly in the form of CrO , and the oxidation reaction for the acidic process is:

$$K_{\text{Cr}} = \frac{a_{\text{CrO}}}{a_{[\text{Cr}] \cdot a_{(\text{FeO})}} = \frac{(\text{CrO})}{[\% \text{Cr}] (\text{FeO})} \cdot \frac{f_{\text{CrO}}}{f_{\text{FeO}}}; \quad (2)$$

Replacing, as a first approximation, the activities of CrO and FeO in the slag with concentrations and expressing the distribution coefficient of chromium, we obtain:

$$(\text{CrO})/[\text{Cr}] = K_{\text{Cr}} (\text{FeO}) \text{ or } 1.31(\text{Cr})/[\text{Cr}] = K_{\text{Cr}} (\text{FeO}); \quad (3)$$

where 1.31 is a coefficient that takes into account the replacement of concentration (CrO) with concentration (Cr).

Consequently, the distribution of chromium between the metal and the slag, i.e. the degree of oxidation of chromium is proportional to the FeO content in the slag. In basic slags, Cr_2O_3 predominates, which, having acidic properties and binding to CaO , is stable in such slags. Therefore, during the main process, the reaction occurs preferentially.

According to experimental data for this reaction:

$$\lg K_{\text{Cr}} = \lg \frac{(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3)}{[\% \text{Cr}]^2 (\text{FeO})^3} = -\frac{19950}{T} + 12.54; \quad (5)$$

When replacing the activities of Cr_2O_3 and FeO in the slag with concentrations, as was done in equation (5), we can simplify it by writing:

$$(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3)/[\text{Cr}]^2 = K_{\text{Cr}} (\text{FeO})^3 \text{ or } 1.47 (\text{Cr})/[\text{Cr}]^2 = K_{\text{Cr}} (\text{FeO})^3; \quad (6)$$

where 1.47 is a coefficient that takes into account the replacement of concentration (Cr_2O_3) by concentration (Cr).

Consequently, during the main process, the distribution coefficient of chromium between the metal and the slag, which characterizes the degree of its oxidation, increases with increasing FeO content in the slag [15-17].

Results.

Since Cr_2O_3 , having acidic properties, binds with CaO in the slag into quasi-molecules, with increasing basicity the activity of chromium oxides decreases, and this causes an increase in its distribution coefficient between the slag and the metal (Fig. 1). However, the role of slag basicity appears to manifest itself not only in its direct influence on the activity coefficient of chromium oxides. As noted above and can be seen in the activity change curves (FeO), also plotted in Fig. 1, almost to the value of $(\% \text{CaO})/(\% \text{SiO}_2) = 3$, a simultaneous increase in

α_{FeO} and $(\% \text{Cr}) / [\% \text{Cr}]$ is observed. But with a further increase in basicity, its direct influence on the chromium distribution coefficient predominates - it also increases under conditions of decreased activity of iron monoxide.

Fig. 1. The influence of slag basicity on the chromium distribution coefficient (1) and the activity of iron monoxide at (FeO) 10% (2) and 30% (3): points - experimental data related to curve 1.

As follows from equation (5), temperature has a significant influence on the distribution coefficient of chromium between slag and metal: with increasing temperature it decreases. Consequently, with decreasing temperature, the equilibrium content of chromium in the metal decreases, and more complete oxidation of chromium dissolved in the metal occurs.

Conclusion.

Conclusion is in order. To increase the activity of Cr_2O_3 and, as a result, obtain a greater degree of chromium reduction, i.e. less waste; when smelting high-chromium [$\text{Cr} > 14\%$] stainless steel in arc furnaces, the slag of the oxidation period has low basicity: $\text{CaO } 10\text{...}15\%$; $\text{SiO}_2 \text{ } 15\text{...}20\%$; $(\% \text{CaO}) / (\% \text{SiO}_2) = 0.7\text{...}1.0$. But, such slag FeO has a significant effect on the distribution coefficient of chromium between the slag and the metal: with increasing content (FeO), this coefficient increases, i.e. chromium waste increases during the smelting process. This effect of iron monoxide is obvious when analyzing equation (5).

References

1. Nozimjon Kholmiraev, Bakhtiyor Kasimov, Bahodirjon Abdullayev, Asatov Sunnatillo, & Abdullaev Farrux. (2021). INCREASING THE LIFETIME OF TILLAGE MACHINE OF PLOWSHARES MADE STEEL MADE BY FOUNDRY TECHNOLOGIES. *JournalNX - A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal*, 7(11), 55–59. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/QB5TF>
2. Turakhodjaev, N., Kholmiraev, N., Saidkhodjaeva, S., & Kasimov, B. (2021). Quality improvement of the steel melting technology in an electric arc furnace. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(7), 48-54.
3. Nosir, S., Nodir, T., Kamol, A., Nozimjon, K., & Nuritdin, T. (2022). Development of quality steel alloy liquidation technology. *American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 7, 74-83.
4. Kholmiraev, N., Turakhodjaev, N., & Sadikova, N. (2023). Improvement of the Melting Technology of 35XГCJI Brand Steel Alloy in An Electric ARC Furnace. *Role of Exact and Natural Sciences During the Renaissance III*, 60-64.

5. Turakhodjaev, N. (2022). Technology for cleaning non-metallic inclusions and gaseous pores in the process of liquefaction of steels in an electric arc furnace. *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science*, 4, 77-82.
6. Kholmiraev, N., Abdullaev, F., Turakhodjaev, N., Akramov, M., & Makhamatmuratov, U. (2022). Development of Technology of Mading Shafts from 35XGCL Brand Steel Alloy.
7. Kholmiraev, N., Turakhodjaev, N., Saidmakhamadov, N., Khasanov, J., Saidkhodjaeva, S., & Sadikova, N. (2023). Development of Technology of Making Shafts from Steel Alloy 35XGCL. *Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, 762 LNNS. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-40628-7_18
8. Kholmiraev, N., Khasanov, J., Abdullayev, B., Saidkhodjaeva, S., Bektemirov, A., Sadikova, N., ... & Nurdinov, Z. (2024). Improving the technology of obtaining highquality castings from steel in sand-clay molds. In *E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 525, p. 03012)*. EDP Sciences.
9. Kholmiraev, N., Turakhodjaev, N., Saidmakhamadov, N., Khasanov, J., Bektemirov, A., & Sadikova, N. (2024). Effects of titanium (Ti) contents on the wear resistance of low-alloy steel alloys. In *E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 525, p. 03003)*. EDP Sciences.
10. Nodir T. et al. Development of 280X29Ni Alloy Liquefaction Technology to Increase the Hardness and Corrosion Resistance of Cast Products //International Journal of Mechatronics and Applied Mechanics. – 2021. – T. 154. – C. 2021.
11. Nosir S. et al. DEVELOPMENT OF QUALITY STEEL ALLOY LIQUIDATION TECHNOLOGY //American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development. – 2022. – T. 7. – C. 74-83.
12. Nosir S. et al. Development of technology for obtaining quality castings from steel alloys //Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology. – 2022. – T. 5. – C. 135-138.
13. Nosir S. et al. Technology to Increase the Hardness and Resistance of High–Chromium White Cast Iron //European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science. – 2022. – T. 6. – C. 665 – 670.
14. Norkhudjayev, F. R., Mukhamedov, A. A., Djalolova, S. T., Ergashev, D. M., & Hudayberdiyev, O. R. (2020). Technological capabilities of application of thermocyclic processing (Тср) tool steel. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(8), 1866-1874.
15. Norkhudjayev, F. R., Mukhamedov, A. A., & Ergashev, D. M. (2019). FEATURES OF THERMAL PROCESSING OF INSTRUMENTAL ALLOYED STEELS. *Journal of Tashkent Institute of Railway Engineers*, 15(2), 68-71.
16. Норхуджаев, Ф. Р., & Эргашев, Д. М. (2020). ТЕРМОЦИКЛИЧЕСКАЯ ОБРАБОТКА (ТЦО) НЕТЕПЛОСТОЙКИХ ИНСТРУМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ СТАЛЕЙ. *Universum: технические науки*, (11-1 (80)), 73-77.
17. Norkhudjayev, F. R., Mukhamedov, A. A., Khudayberdiyev, O. R., Ergashev, D. M., & Norkhudjayeva, R. F. (2020). Development of Machine-Building Materials and Details of Machines from the Powders received from Waste of Raw Materials in the Industry of Uzbekistan. *Test Engineering and Management*, 83(5-6), 639-646.